

Extractive spectrophotometric determination of manganese(II) using 4-(methylphenyl)-3-oxobutanamide

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A simple, sensitive, rapid and selective method is proposed for the spectrophotometric determination of manganese(II) in trace amount using 4-(methylphenyl)-3-oxobutanamide as a complexing agent and extracting the red coloured 1 : 2 complex into chloroform from aqueous solution of pH 4.5–5.6. The complex shows $\lambda_{\max}$ at 445 nm and obeys Beer's law in the concentration range 0.74–10.32 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. Molar absorptivity of the complex and Sandell's sensitivity of the method are 4972 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ and 0.011 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively. The method has been applied satisfactorily to the analysis of various synthetic samples and alloys.

Organic ligands with β -diketo group constitute an important class of reagents used in the analysis of various metal ions. One such ligand was investigated¹ for gravimetric determination of Mn^{II} . 4-(ζ -Pyridylazo)resorcinol², 2-(5-bromopyridylazo)-5-(diethylaminophenol)³, chromeazurol S³, bis(2,4,4-trimethylpentyl)monothio phosphinic acid⁴, 5,8-dihydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinone⁵ have been used for spectrophotometric determination of Mn^{II} . Manganese in various sources like effluent stream⁶, tea leave⁷ was determined spectrophotometrically after prior oxidation by sodium bismuthate. In this investigation, a ligand containing β -diketo group, *p*-methylacetoacetanilide has been used for prior complexation and extraction of Mn^{II} quantitatively into chloroform. Measuring absorbance of the extracted coloured complex, spectrophotometric determination of Mn^{II} has been studied in presence of various metal ions.

Results and discussion

Manganese(II) formed a red coloured complex with the reagent. In acidic medium the complex was extractable into chloroform. The complex had two absorbance maxima at 390 and 445 nm, where the reagent had slight absorbance. Further work was done at 445 nm. The effect of pH on the absorbance of manganese(II) complex was studied using sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer and 1.0 *N* sodium hydroxide solution. Complete extraction was observed at pH 4.5–5.6. Only 3.0 mg reagent per ml of aqueous phase was sufficient for quantitative extraction of manganese(II) in the range 0.37–5.20 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of the aqueous phase.

The absorbance of the metal complex in different organic solvents, immiscible in water, decreased in the order : diethyl ether > chloroform > carbon tetrachloride > amyl

alcohol > isobutyl methyl ketone. Maintaining organic solvent and water phase volume ratio 1 : 2, the extraction of the complex was 100% with ether and chloroform, 95% with carbon tetrachloride, 74% with amyl alcohol and 57% with isobutyl methyl ketone. Because of the greater stability of the complex in chloroform, it was used as extracting solvent. Shaking time of 2–3 min was optimum for transferring the complex quantitatively to the organic phase in a single extraction. The complex was found stable for 3.5 h in chloroform.

Beer's law was obeyed over the concentration range 0.74–10.32 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of the extract, as obtained from the Ringbom curve at 445 nm. For ten replicate determinations of 8.85 $\mu\text{g Mn}^{\text{II}}$ per ml of extract, the relative standard deviation was 1.36%. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were 4972 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ and 0.011 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively. The composition of the complex, investigated by Job's method of continuous variation as modified by Vosburgh and Cooper⁸, showed that the metal ion and the ligand were present in the ratio 1 : 2 in the extracted species. Infrared spectra (KBr) of the reagent and the complex exhibited bands at 1603 and 1580 cm^{-1} , respectively. The shift of the bands to lower frequency region indicated coordination of the metal ion through 1 : 2 diketo group in enol form.

Effect of diverse ions : The effect of various anions, cations and complexing agents (added in $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ aqueous phase, shown in the parenthesis) was studied by taking 4.425 mg ml^{-1} of Mn^{II} in aqueous phase under the optimum condition. Sulfate (10), chloride (10), phosphate (0.025), fluoride (4), tungstate (0.01), molybdate (0.02) and citric acid (5) when added before the addition of the reagent,

caused the error of <1% Disodium EDTA, sulfosalicylic acid, tartaric acid and thioglycolic acid interfered seriously Ca^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Hg^{II} , Zn^{II} , Pb^{II} (0.025 each) Ba^{II} , Cd^{II} , Al^{III} , VO^{II} (0.05 each) Mg^{II} (0.005) Fe^{III} (0.003) and Cu^{II} (1.5) did not affect the absorbance of the complex

Table I Determination of Mn in synthetic samples and alloys

Synthetic samples

Sl no	Composition mg	Mn added μg	Proposed method	
			Mn found* μg	RSD % $\pm$
1	Al (0.04) Zn (0.02) Cu (0.40)	88.5	89.1	1.06
2	Pb (0.02) Br (0.03) VO (0.03)	88.5	88.2	1.40
3	Ca (0.04) Cd (0.04)	88.5	88.4	0.73
4	Fe (0.025) ^a	88.5	88.4	1.07
5	Cu (0.48) Ni (0.024) Fe (0.006) ^b	88.5	89.3	1.40

Alloy samples

Sl no	Sample	Mn certified %	Mn found* %	RSD % $\pm$
2	Alloy steel no. 3333 (Gun and Shell Factory Ichapur)	0.58	0.58	0.54

* Average of duplicate analysis

^aComposition analogous to ferromanganese ^bComposition analogous to manganin

Application The results of applicability of the proposed method to several synthetic samples and steels (Table I) were satisfactory and the method was found simple and quick with good sensitivity

Mild steel sample (1.02 g) was boiled with conc. HNO_3 (10 ml) and heated to fumes with conc. H_2SO_4 (3 ml). After dilution and filtration the volume was made up to 100 ml. From 10 ml of this solution Mn was removed by precipitation (basic formate method)⁹, and the filtrate was made up to 100 ml. A 10 ml portion of this final solution was used for the determination of manganese. Alloy steel sample (0.9956 g) was treated in a similar way.

Experimental

A Systronics 118 UV vis spectrophotometer with 10 ml

matched quartz cells, a Perkin-Elmer 1330 IR spectrophotometer and a Systronics 306 pH meter were used. Solutions of Mn^{II} and other cations were prepared from their chloride or sulfate salts. For anions, sodium, potassium or ammonium salts were taken. 4-(Methylphenyl)-3-oxobutanamide was synthesized¹⁰ and dissolved in ethanol to make 3% (w/v) solution. Sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer solution was used to adjust the pH of complexation and extraction.

Procedure An aliquot of a standard solution containing 7.375–103.250 μg of Mn^{II} was diluted to 16 ml to which the reagent solution (3% 2 ml) was added and pH adjusted to 4.5–5.6 by adding a buffer solution (2 ml). The mixture was shaken for 3 min and equilibrated with chloroform (10 ml). The organic phase was separated and dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate. Absorbance of the red complex was measured at 445 nm against a reagent blank. The Ringbom curve was drawn.

During the study of diverse ion effect, solution containing a particular amount of the ion was mixed with an aliquot of standard manganese(II) solution and the procedure was repeated as above.

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